

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

^{ab}Lopresto V.*, ^aLangella A., ^{ab}Leone C., ^{ab}Caprino G., ^aVillani G.

^aDept. of Chemicals, Materials and Production Engineering, ^bCIRTIBS Research Centre, University of Naples "Federico II", P.le Tecchio 80 – 80125 Naples, Italy.

* lopresto@unina.it

Keywords: *impact; absorbed energy; basalt fibre, delamination.*

1 Abstract

At the aim to investigate about the dynamic response of a new composite material made of basalt fibre in epoxy resin, low velocity impact tests were carried out on specimens different in thickness. The results of the tests at complete penetration so that at different impact energy levels were used to investigate about the influence of the impact parameters: the maximum force, F_{max} , was found to be a good one to compare data obtained in different conditions. The absorbed energy was evaluated too, together with the impact energy and the penetration one, giving the possibility to individuate a threshold value below which no damage is present in the laminate. Particular attention was paid on the internal damage: a deply technique was adopted to evaluate the delamination extension and the fibre failure length at each interface. The effect of a low velocity impact is localized around the impact area and a small extension of the delamination was observed denoting a different way of energy absorption.

2 Introduction

Many studies were devoted to understanding the response of composite materials to impact, identifying the damage mechanisms [1-5] and their effect on residual properties [3,6,7]. However, many aspects remain quite obscure yet like the way through which the initial energy of the projectile is absorbed by the laminate. The absorption of irreversible energy plays a fundamental role in the development of composite materials with improved impact resistance. For example, Sutherland and Guedes Soares [8] and Delfosse and Poursartip [9] tried to identify the mechanisms of energy absorption in a laminate during low-velocity impact, correlating the energy loss with the observed failure modes.

In the present work, following the approach of the above mentioned authors and analyzing the results of impact tests carried out on basalt fibre laminates in different thicknesses, it was tried to identify the internal damage caused by an accidental dynamic load of a material not so much studied yet. After the experimental tests, the specimens were deplied and the delamination and the fibre failures were measured layer by layer and were correlated to the impact energy. Interestingly, a different mechanism of delamination propagation along the thickness together with small damage area were observed. The latter was found to be concentrated under material-impactor contact point. An energy threshold value, below which no damage is present in the laminate, was individuated.

3 Materials and test methods

Impact tests were carried out on basalt fibre reinforced plastics (BFRP). Laminates, 300 mm x 300 mm in plane dimensions, were obtained through infusion technology. The reinforcement employed is basalt dry fabrics, 200 g/m², plain-weave, in epoxy matrix, Becor SX10M + Hardness SX10M. A sufficient number of plies were overlapped following the stacking sequence: [(0,90)/(+45,-45)]_{ns}, with n=2 to 4, leading to nominal thickness of 1, 2 and 3 mm and a fibre volume fraction $V_f = 50\%$. From the laminates, square specimens 70 mm in side were cut by a diamond saw.

Impact test were carried out on a drop weight testing machine, Ceast Fractovis MK4, using a semi-spherical nose indenter, 19.8 mm in diameter. The samples were simply supported on a steel plate with a circular opening 50 mm in diameter, and struck at their centre. To avoid multiple impacts, the tup was caught on the rebound by a brake available in the testing machine.

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

A first series of tests, to obtain the complete Force-displacement (F-d) curve up to penetration, was carried out.

Then, at the aim to investigate about the damage start and propagation, three characteristic energy levels in correspondence of characteristic points on the increasing part of the load curve, were selected. These points, highlighted by changing in slope or load drops on the curve, are related to what happens inside the material in terms of damages. Since the most significant failure modes was often found on the increasing first part of the load curve [10-12], the variable energy values were chosen on the impact curve up to the maximum force.

In this second series of tests, labeled as indentation tests, the chosen energy levels were reproduced by combining the drop height and three masses ($M=3.6, 5.6, 7.6$ kg).

At least three impact tests were performed for each experimental condition.

At the aim to study the ply-by-ply damage extent and type, a small hole 1 mm in diameter was drilled at the impact point of some selected specimens. They were, then, immersed in a dye penetrant until the projected delaminated area was completely imbibed by the red ink (see Fig. 1). At the end, the specimens were dried for a time, and carefully deplied with the help of moderate heating. The delaminated area in correspondence of each interlaminar surface was measured by CAD software, and the in-plane length of broken fibres was evaluated by an optical microscopy. Since the very difficult and long procedure, just one specimen per each condition was deplied.

Fig. 1. Darker area representing delamination in a single layer after deplying.

4 Results

4.1 Load curve

Typical impact curves recorded during the perforation tests, obtained for various panel thicknesses, t , are collected in Fig. 2. Irrespective of t , all the curves reveal common features. At low displacement, the material behaviour is elastic, but contrary to what often found [10-13] it is not disturbed by significant dynamic oscillations that usually are more marked, the thicker the panel is. Another difference noted is the lack of the sequence of sudden load drops at a sufficient high load, generally indicating significant failure. For this reason, not more than three points were selected on this part of the curve to obtain the energy levels for the indentation tests.

Around the peak load, load drops, suggesting major damage, are observed. Finally, the force begins to smoothly decrease, until the complete perforation.

For a fixed displacement, an increase in panel thickness, t , results in a clear increase in the contact force and in initial rigidity (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Typical force-displacement curves recorded during the perforation tests. Different thickness.

4.2 Delaminated area

The ply-by-ply damage was quantified by the total delaminated area, A_t , determined as the sum of all the delaminated areas, layer by layer, evidenced by the red ink after deplying, and the total length of broken fibres, A_f . With the symbol A_{max} , the maximum in plane extension of the delaminated area, also called projected delaminated area [13], was indicated. Generally, delaminations are generated from the cracks in the matrix at interfaces between plies with different orientations, mainly

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

propagating in the direction of the fibres in the lower ply, and extending the more, the larger is their distance from the contact point [13]. This, usually, is more pronounced in thin laminates where the bending effect produces delaminations in the opposite layers respect to the contact point [16]. In the present case, very small delaminations were found on the specimens 1 mm in thickness (Fig.3). Of course, at the increasing of the impact energy, larger delaminations were observed. However, looking at Fig. 3, only for very low impact energy no damage was found under the impactor contact point (left side in the figure) whereas, as expected, it increases along the thickness up to the opposite side. The higher energies allow delaminations under the contact point, maximum in the middle and nil on the opposite side. This behavior is very similar to what happen, in general, for thick laminates, where the bending effect is negligible and the contact force assumes an important role.

Fig. 3. Delaminated area layer by layer: t = 1 mm.

In Figs. 4 and 5, the delaminated areas layer by layer at the increasing impact energy, were shown for the laminates 2 and 3 mm in thickness. In these two thicker laminates, delamination was always found in each layer, also between layers with the same orientation. In both cases, for the two lower impact energy values, the delamination is maximum in the middle whereas it assumes more or less the same lower extension in the external layers. The higher impact energy generates a more constant trend of delamination propagation along the thickness, irrespective of the orientation between two successive plies.

Fig. 4. Delaminated area layer by layer: t = 2 mm.

Fig. 5. Delaminated area layer by layer: t = 3 mm.

In Figs. 6, a comparison between the layer by layer extent of the damage in glass and basalt laminates with the same stacking sequence and in the same test conditions, is reported.

Fig. 6. Delamination layer by layer: comparison between basalt (square symbols) and glass (rhombus symbols) laminates. t = 3 mm.

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

The difference in the distribution along the thickness of the delamination, more constant for the basalt composites, denotes a different energy absorption mechanism. Moreover, glass laminates showed no delamination between some layers in the middle and the maximum delaminated area on glass laminates is larger than the basalt one.

In Figs. 7 and 8, the total delaminated area, A_t , and the maximum in plane extension of delamination, A_{max} , are plotted against the impact energy, U : linear trends, different in slope for each analyzed thickness, were observed.

Fig. 7. Total delaminated area, A_t , as a function of impact energy, U .

Fig. 8. Maximum delaminated area, A_t , as a function of impact energy, U .

At the aim to find the right parameter to compare data obtained in different conditions, very useful for the prediction models, as already done for the

indentation depth [14, 15], the total delaminated area was plotted against the non dimensional energy, U/U_p (Fig. 9). Contrary to what found in [14, 15], the data are separated again denoting the inappropriate role of the non dimensional energy in comparing data from different conditions. The same was noted for the projected delaminated area.

Moreover, for a fixed impact energy, increasing the thickness results in larger delamination extent. This behaviour is in contrast with what usually found for glass and carbon laminates [13, 16] denoting again a different way to absorb the impact energy.

Fig. 9. Total delaminated area, A_t , as a function of the non dimensional energy, U/U_p .

The same data from Figs. 7 and 8 were, then, plotted against the maximum load (Figs. 10 and 11), F_{max} : a single linear trend, irrespective of the thickness, was observed. It means that the maximum force could be the right parameter to compare data obtained in different conditions. Also in [12, 16, 17], the force instead of the energy was studied to predict the impact behaviour, in terms of damage, on composites.

The equation:

$$A_t = 0.4862 F_{max} - 1591.7 \quad (1)$$

obtained by best fitting the experimental points, graphically represents the solid line in Fig. 10, whose minimum coefficient of correlation was $R^2=0.97$.

Putting $A_t=0$ in Eq. (1), the intercept of the straight line with the x axis, $F_{max}= 3274$ N, is easily calculated. This represents the threshold value for the beginning of the damage and it means that below this value of maximum load no delamination is

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

present in the laminate, whichever the panel thickness.

Fig. 10. Total delamination, A_t , vs. maximum force, F_{max} .

Fig.11. Projected delamination, A_{max} , vs. maximum load, F_{max} .

The same procedure was adopted in figure 11 where the maximum extent of the delaminated area was reported against the maximum load. $F_{max} = 2800$ N was found as the x intercept and considering the possible errors made in measuring the delamination extensions in both the techniques, the value can be considered very close to what obtained for A_{tot} .

As noted for other laminate configurations [9, 18], a linear trend also correlates the projected and total delaminated areas (Fig. 12). Therefore, knowing A_{max} gives a good belief of the actual delamination occurring in the material.

However, looking at the slopes in Fig. 12, it is possible to assert that the same projected

delamination implies a total delaminated area being the larger, the thicker the composite is. This confirms what noted in Figs. 7-9 denoting a different behaviour respect to the classical laminates [13, 16].

Fig. 12. Projected delamination, A_{max} , vs. total delaminated area, A_t .

However, looking at figure 13 where the same data from Fig. 12 are reported, it seems that, with a very good approximation ($R^2=0.98$), it is possible to believe that also a single linear trend could fit all the data showed in the previous figure, irrespective of the thickness. Since the slope of the curve, drawn by hand for simplicity, decreases at the increasing of the total delamination, it highlights the importance to know exactly what happen inside the laminate along the thickness respect to what is observable in plane. The maximum extent of the damage tends, in fact, to grow slower whereas inside the material the damage becomes more serious. Of course, more data are necessary to be sure of the exact behavior.

Fig. 13: Projected delaminated area, A_{max} , against total delaminated area, A_t . Single linear trend.

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

In Fig. 14, the length of the delamination, D , obtained by a microscopic observation the section passing through the centre of the impact point, was plotted against the impact energy. In agreement with what found for classical laminates [13, 16], in correspondence of the same impact energy, the length of delamination is the larger the thinner the laminate is (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. Delamination length, D , against impact energy, U .

This is apparently in contrast with what found about the delaminated area. However, it is necessary to consider that the length of the delamination was measured in correspondence of a section of the specimen obtained by a cut passing through the impact point along one direction (figure 15). Since the shape of the lobe of the delamination along the fibre direction, the cut along the perpendicular direction could be larger or smaller than what measured and so, it could change the trend.

Fig. 15: Magnification of a cross section. $t = 3$ mm, $U = 20$ J. Arrow: impact side.

Usually [10-12], the most severe impact damages were found on the first part of the load curve up to the maximum force.

Fig. 16: Projected delaminated area, A_{max} , against the maximum load, F_{max} . Comparison with penetrated specimens.

This is the reason that lead to choose the variable energy levels, useful to investigate about the damage start and propagation, on this increasing part of the load curve. However, comparing the delamination extents measured on the penetrated laminates, with the measured values obtained in correspondence of the impact tests at different energy values, in figure 16, a significant larger extent on the penetrated specimens was observed denoting a severe damage propagation also after the maximum load. This, again, represents a different impact behaviour of basalt laminates that showed the ability to work also after the maximum force.

4.3 Absorbed energy

In [19], the measured non-dimensional values U_a/U_p , where U_a represents the absorbed energy for damage creation and U_p the penetration one, for laminates like the ones analyzed here, were plotted against U/U_p and a bi-linear trend was evidenced. As highlighted by Sutherland and Guedes Soares [8], the knee of the bilinear trend denotes the onset of fibre damage. It was found in correspondence of $U \sim 0.16U_p$ for basalt laminates: for an energy equal to 16% of the penetration energy, the fibre failure starts. This value is lower than CFRP laminates but higher than glass fibre ones, denoting a better behaviour respect to glass fibre.

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

However, the same data was reconsidered here and a single linear trend was thought to better fit the experimental data (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17. Non dimensional absorbed energy, U_a/U_p , against non dimensional impact energy, U/U_p .

The following equation:

$$U_a/U_p = 0.8722U/U_p - 0.0897 \quad (2)$$

obtained by best fitting the experimental points, graphically represents the solid line in Fig. 17 whose minimum coefficient of correlation was $R^2=0.94$.

Putting $U_a/U_p=0$ in Eq. (3), the intercept of the straight line with the x axis, $U/U_p=0.103$, is easily calculated. Therefore, when the initial energy is lower than a threshold value, in the present case 10% of the perforation energy, a perfectly elastic impact should occur, whichever the panel thickness. At 10% of the penetration energy, the first damage starts in the impacted laminate under matrix crack and delamination form [1, 9, 20-23]. It is so conceivable that, after that and in correspondence of 16% of U_p , the fibre begin to failure [19].

4.4 Fibre failure

The total length of fibre failure, as the sum of the fibre failures in each layer observed by an optical microscope, was reported against the impact energy in Fig. 18.

As it can be simply deduced by the graph, no significant fibre failures were found in the thinnest laminates, $t = 1$ mm, as they was not reported. This could be due to the bending effect that allow the absorption of all the energy necessary for the damage, producing in this case only delamination. For the thicker laminates, a linear trend was

observed, with the length of fibre failure increasing at the increasing of the thickness.

Fig.18: Fibre failure length, l , against impact energy, U .

The variation of visible broken fibre length with U is substantially linear,

In Fig. 19, the total length of fibre failure is reported as a function of the total delaminated area.

Fig.19. Fibre failure length, l , against total delaminated area, A_t .

As already found [13], the single trend, highlighted by the solid line, suggests that the general damage state (i.e. the overall quantity of delaminated areas and the broken fibres in the material volume) can be described by a single parameter, independently of the composite thickness.

By comparing the load forces and the broken fibre length (Fig. 20), an interesting result was observed: the fibre begin to broke as the force approach its

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

maximum value, where significant oscillations were found.

Fig. 20. Fiber failure length location on the impact load curve.

As already said at the beginning of the paper, when the shape of the F-d curve was described, differences were found with classical trends of the load curves. Here, in fact, the curves are not disturbed by significant dynamic oscillations nor for the thicker panels and they don't present the sequence of sudden load drops at a sufficient high load, generally indicating significant failure. The latter are present only around the peak load where the experimental points, indicating broken fibres, are located. It could confirm the usefulness of the load curve in giving information about the internal damage and underline the different damage mechanism of the basalt laminates respect to carbon and glass ones.

4. Conclusions

With the present work, a tentative was done to understand the impact behaviour of a new composite materials, made by basalt fibre, not so much investigated yet. From the general results, it seems that its behavior in terms of internal damage, as a consequence of a dynamic load, is better than classical composites.

From the results of low velocity impacts on laminates different in thickness, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

- delaminations were found in each layer also with the same orientation and more uniformly distributed along the thickness at the increasing of the impact energy;

- a different way to absorb the impact energy was noted since the increasing of the thickness resulted in larger delamination extent;
- the maximum force was found to be the right parameter to compare data obtained in different conditions. The threshold load value for the beginning of the delamination was individuated too;
- the ability of basalt laminates to continue to support loads also after the maximum force was highlighted by larger delamination extents after the maximum peak of the load curve;
- the energy values for the beginning of delamination and fibre fracture were individuated;
- the importance of the load curve as a map of the impact behaviour was highlighted here since fibre failure were correlated with the oscillations around F_{max} .

Of course, these conclusions are obtained on the base of few investigations since the difficult and long technique. It would be very interesting in the future to validate them with more data.

5. References

- [1] G Schoeppner, S Abrate. "Delamination threshold loads for low velocity impact on composite laminates", *Composites Part A*, Vol.31, 2000, pp. 903–915.
- [2] CF Li, N Hu, JG Cheng, H Fukunaga, H Sekine. "Low-velocity impact-induced damage of continuous fiber-reinforced composite laminates. Part II. Verification and numerical investigation", *Composites Part A*, Vol. 33, 2002, pp. 1063–1072.
- [3] GAO Davies, R Olsson. "Impact on composite structures", *Aeronaut. Journal*, Vol. 108, 2004, pp. 541–563.
- [4] JN Baucom, MA Zikry. "Low-velocity impact damage progression in woven E-glass composite systems", *Composites Part A*, Vol. 36, 2005, pp. 658–664.
- [5] OS David-West, DH Nash, WM Banks. "An experimental study of damage accumulation in balanced CFRP laminates due to repeated impact", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 83, 2008, pp. 247–258.
- [6] P Feraboli, KT Kedward. "Enhanced evaluation of the low-velocity impact response of composite plates", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 42, 2004, pp. 2143–2152
- [7] J-H Byun, S-W Song, C-H Lee, M-K Um, B-S Hwang. "Impact properties of laminated composites with stitching fibers", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 76, 2006, pp. 21–27.

IRREVERSIBLY ABSORBED ENERGY AND DAMAGE IN BFRP LAMINATES IMPACTED AT LOW-VELOCITY

- [8] LS Sutherland, C Guedes Soares. "Impact of low fibre-volume, glass/polyester rectangular plates", *Composite Structures*, Vol. 68, 2005, pp. 13-22.
- [9] D Delfosse, A Poursartip. "Energy-based approach to impact damage in CFRP laminates", *Composites Part A*, Vol. 28A, 1997, pp. 647-655.
- [10] G. Caprino, V. Lopresto, C. Scarponi, G. Briotti. "Influence of material thickness on the response of graphite fabric/epoxy panels to low velocity impact", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 59, 1999, pp. 2279-2286.
- [11] M.N. Ghasemi Nejhada and A. Parvizi-Majidi, "Impact behaviour and damage tolerance of woven carbon fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites", *Composites*, Vol. 21, 1990, pp. 155-168.
- [12] W.C. Jackson, C.C. Jr. Poe, "The use of impact force as a scale parameter for the impact response of composite laminates", *J. of Composite Technology & Research, JCTRER*, Vol. 15, 1993, pp. 282-289.
- [13] G. Caprino, V. Lopresto, A. Langella, M. Durante. "Irreversibly absorbed energy and damage in GFRP laminates impacted at low-velocity", *etdcm9- 9th International Seminar on Experimental Techniques and Design in Composite Materials*, 30 September – 2 October 2009, DTG University of Padova, Vicenza (Italy).
- [14] G. Caprino, V. Lopresto, "The significance of indentation in the inspection of carbon fibre reinforced plastic panels damaged by low-velocity impact", *Comp. Science and Technol.*, Vol. 60, 2000, pp. 1003-1012.
- [15] G. Caprino, A. Langella, V. Lopresto, "Indentation and penetration of carbon fibre reinforced plastic laminates", *Composites Part. B*, Vol. 34, 2003, pp. 319-25.
- [16] G. Caprino, V. Lopresto, "Macroscopic behaviour and fracture modes of CFRP panels transversely loaded at the centre" *ECCM11*, 2004, Rhodes, Greece.
- [17] R. Olsson, M.V. Donadon, B.G. Falzon, "Delamination threshold load for dynamic impact on plates", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 43, 2006, pp. 3124–3141.
- [18] MV Hosur, CRL Murthy, TS Ramamurthy, A Shet, "Estimation of impact-induced damage in CFRP laminates through ultrasonic imaging", *NDT&E Int.*, Vol. 31, 1998, pp. 359-374.
- [19] G. Caprino, V. Lopresto, A. Langella and C. Leone, "Damage and Energy Absorption in GFRP laminates impacted at low-velocity: Indentation Model", *Procedia Engineering*, Vol. 10 (2011), pp. 2298–2311.
- [20] Choi H.Y. and Chang F.K., "A model for predicting damage in graphite/epoxy laminated composites resulting from low-velocity point impact", *J. of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 14, 1992, pp. 2134-2169.
- [21] F.K. Chang, H.Y. Choi, and H.S. Wang, "Damage of laminated composites due to low velocity impact", *31st AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Struct. Dyn. and Mater. Conf.*, Long Beach, CA, April 2-4, 1990, pp. 930-940.
- [22] G. Caprino, A. Langella and V. Lopresto, "Elastic behaviour of circular composite plates transversely loaded at the centre", *Composites Part A*, Vol. 33, 2002, pp. 1191-1197.
- [23] S. Liu, Z. Kutlu, and F.K. Chang, "Matrix cracking and delamination propagation in laminated composites subjected to transversely concentrated loading", *J. Compos. Mater.*, Vol. 27, No. 5, 1993, pp. 436-470.